

Composites in the Sea: Sorption, Strength and Fatigue

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SUMMARY: This article presents long term experimental data regarding several aspects of the sorption characteristics of sea water in graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy polymeric composites. In addition, the article provides results regarding the effects of sea water on the strengths and fatigue lives of the above composite systems. This article is an abbreviated version of a recent technical report with the same title^[1].

KEYWORDS: Polymeric composites. Fluid sorption. Sea water effects. Strength. Fatigue.

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites are utilized to an increasing degree in naval and off-shore structures. Consequently, the effects of sea water on the integrity of these materials are of significant current interest since losses in material integrity are strongly reflected in durability under load.

For a large class of composite materials, exposed to many fluids under a wide range of circumstances, it has been noted that material integrity can be correlated with certain characteristic features of fluid weight-gain data^[2]. Such features are exhibited by the schematic weight-gain vs. square root of time curves A, B, C, and D in Fig. 1, with comparison against predictions of linear Fickian diffusion theory shown by the curve LF. It was noted that weight-gain data featured by curves A and B are generally associated with “benign” effects on material properties, limited in scope and most likely reversible upon fluid desorption. On the other hand, weight-gain data along curves C and D in Fig. 1 are indicative of severe and irreversible fluid-induced degradations of materials integrity, portending the advent of failure.

This article presents long-term sorption data of sea water for graphite/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites, demonstrating that both materials systems are subject to irreversible degradations when exposure exceeds three years. Additional data concern the effects of static and cyclic hydrostatic pressures as well as of material aging on the sorption of sea water in polymeric composites. Finally, it is shown that fatigue life under immersed conditions is shorter than that under fatigue-in-air, with a drastic reduction for glass fiber systems.

SORPTION BEHAVIOR

Long term sorption data for two graphite/epoxy and one glass epoxy systems are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. Note the weight losses and abrupt weight-gains, respectively, that occur after about three years of exposure. The data in Fig. 2 follow curve D, and those in Fig. 3 resemble

curve C in Fig. 1, both cases indicative of irreversible, sea water induced property degradations.

Typical effects of hydrostatic pressure on sorption of sea water in polymeric composites are demonstrated in Figs. 4 and 5. Note that while pressure enhances the amount absorbed of sea water, from approximately 1.3% in Fig. 2 to about 1.9% in Fig. 4, pressure cycling has no discernible effect on the above amount.

Another study aimed at separating the effect of prior exposure to moisture from that of spontaneous time aging on the sorption of sea water in polymeric composites. Accounting for the above effects was obtained employing the following procedure:

Pre-dried coupons were divided into two groups. The first group of samples was immersed in sea water for a duration t_0 until near saturation, and then redried in the presence of a desiccant for an additional period t_1 until attaining a steady weight.

Simultaneously, a second group of specimens was held in the initially dry environment for the duration $t_2 = t_0 + t_1$.

At time $t = t_2$ all the coupons in both groups were immersed in sea water in what amounted to a second immersion for the “moisture aged” first group and an initial immersion of the “time aged” second group.

Sorption data were collected for AS4/3501-6 gr/ep, for E-glass/SP1003, and for E-glass/NTC 301 polymeric composite systems. All materials exhibited a marked increase in absorption rate during the second immersion such as exhibited for gr/ep in Fig. 6. The glass/epoxy systems also attained higher saturated levels. On the other hand, an effect of “time aging” was noted only for the E-glass/NTC 301 system, as shown in Fig. 7. Even so, that “time aging” effect was still smaller than that of “moisture aging”, as can be seen from Fig. 8.

FATIGUE RESPONSE

The effects of sea water on the fatigue response of gr/ep and gl/ep composites are demonstrated by comparing the fatigue lives of dry coupons fatigued in air and pre-saturated coupons fatigued under immersed conditions. These are shown in Figs. 9 and 10, respectively. Note that while the gr/ep material exhibits a reduction of about half a decade in fatigue life the corresponding diminution for gl/ep amounts to three decades. The vast discrepancy between the foregoing two materials is due to the fact that while immersion affects the failure of gr/ep through capillary water ingress^[3], exposure to sea water degrades the fibers in gl/ep systems^[2].

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It has been shown that sustained exposure to sea water causes irreversible degradations of polymeric composites and may lead to drastic reductions in fatigue life. Smaller degradations may occur even earlier, as evidenced by the enhancement of the diffusion process upon the second exposure of pre-saturated and re-dried samples. Some, though not all, of the phenomena reported herein can be modeled analytically^{[4][5][6]}.

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Fig. 1: Schematic curves representing four categories of recorded non-Fickian weight-gain sorption data in polymers and polymeric composites. The solid line, designated by LF, corresponds to linear Fickian diffusion (The numbers along the coordinate axis are relevant for LF only).

Fig.2: Five year sorption data for AS4/3501-6 and IM7/8551-7 coupons immersed in simulated seawater at 34 °C.

Fig.3: Four years weight-gain data for E-glass/NCT301 coupons immersed in simulated seawater

Fig. 4: Weight-gain data at p=3 Ksi for AS4/3501-6 [0⁴]₄ immersed in simulated seawater at R.T.

Fig. 5: Weight gain data under weekly cycling of AS4/3501-6 [0°₄] coupons between 0 and 3 ksi immersed in simulated seawater at R.T.

Fig. 6: Weight-gain data for re-dried moisture-aged and time-aged AS4/3501-6 coupons immersed in simulated seawater at 50 °C.

Fig. 7: Comparisons of weight-gain data for time-aged and un-aged E-glass /NCT301 coupons immersed in simulated seawater at 50°C. The time-aged coupons were immersed after a hold period of 32 weeks.

Fig. 8: Weight-gain data for re-dried moisture-aged and time-aged E-glass/NCT301 coupons immersed in simulated seawater at 50 °C.

Fig. 9: S-N Curves under dry and immersed fatigue of $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3]_s$ AS4/3501-6 coupons with $R=0.3$ (Note: the S-N Curves are connected with the average value at each loading level).

Fig. 10: S-N curves under dry and immersed fatigue of $[0^\circ/90^\circ_3]_s$ E-glass/SP1003 coupons with $R=0.1$.